

THE PHENOMENON OF AN OPEN SOCIETY AND THE TASKS OF EDUCATION IN KARL POPPER'S PHILOSOPHY

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Abstract: In this article, the author examines Karl Popper's concept of an open society and its importance for education. The author analyzes the basic principles of an open society and their importance in education. The importance of Popper's philosophy for the development of the education system of New Uzbekistan is emphasized.

Keywords: education, society, open society, critical thinking, rationality, falsifiability.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada muallif Karl Popperring ochiq jamiyat tushunchasi va uning ta'lim uchun ahamiyati haqida so'z yuritadi. Muallif ochiq jamiyatning asosiy tamoyillari va ularning ta'limdagi ahamiyatini tahlil qiladi. Yangi O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirishda Popper falsafasining ahamiyati ko'rstailgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, jamiyat, ochiq jamiyat, tanqidiy fikrlash, ratsionallik, falsifikatsionizm.

Аннотация: В данной статье автором рассматривается концепция открытого общества Карла Поппера и ее значение для образования. Автор анализирует основные принципы открытого общества и их значение в образовании. Подчеркивается значимость философии Поппера для развития системы образования Нового Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: образование, общество, открытое общество, критическое мышление, рациональность, фальсификационизм.

Today, the education system on a global scale is undergoing significant transformations that are in the context of intercultural changes, which in one way or another also affects social development. Education itself is a phenomenon of intercultural philosophy, and therefore it is important to understand its place in the development of civilization [1, 85]. The philosophy of the 20th century is rich in

various concepts and teachings, but the most influential of them is Karl Popper's concept of an open society, which is a comprehensive philosophy. One of the central places in Popper's concept is education as a tool for the formation of critically minded individuals capable of resisting dogmatism and violence. However, first let's look at what an open society is for Popper.

So, Popper points out that there are two types of societies – open and closed. If a closed society is characterized by total control of the state machine and the absence of individual freedom, then in an open society individuals have freedom of thought, critical judgment and political choice. Such a society is based on the principles of democracy, human rights, rational thinking and reasonable resolution of the basic issues of society. Interestingly, if collectivism is inherent in a closed society, then an open society is characterized by individualism and personal freedom, autonomy from society [2, 7]. One of the main principles of an open society is the falsifiability of various ideas and concepts, hypotheses and theories, which is also the cornerstone of Popper's philosophy of science. The philosopher argues that the ability of society to change and correct its mistakes through rational dialogue is the key to its sustainability and progressive development.

Speaking about an open society and criticizing various political and philosophical models of a closed society, Popper points out that education plays a great role in an open society, since it:

1. Builds the ability of critical thinking.
2. Fosters respect for sound reasoning and intellectual honesty.
3. Teaches the principle of falsifiability and openness of knowledge to revision.
4. Promotes tolerance and respect for pluralism.

At the same time, Popper always criticized dogmatic education, which focuses only on memorizing facts and uncritical perception of information [3, 74]. Instead, Popper proposed a model of education based on dialogue, doubt, and hypothesis testing. And since education is an important foundation of an open society according to Popper, its development is one of the most important tasks for society. It must be said that in the context of post-truth, information wars and the increasing polarization of society, critical education is becoming an important tool for combating manipulation and radical ideologies. Therefore, Popper's ideas about education are more relevant than ever. In addition, the concept of an open society continues to influence educational reforms in one way or another, emphasizing the importance of democratic institutions, freedom of speech and a scientific approach in shaping public opinion.

In the progressive development of the New Uzbekistan, Karl Popper's ideas are becoming particularly important in the further reform of the republic's education, its

inclusion in the global education space and the introduction of innovative teaching methods that are close to the principles of an open society [4, 128]. From the point of view of Popper's ideas, important steps are to increase the political culture of individuals, develop their openness to discussion and strengthen civil society. Popper's open society demands the rejection of blind adherence to traditions and the imposition of the only true views, and the development of pluralism of opinions in the field of education serves the progress of the country.

Karl Popper left a significant legacy in philosophy by developing the concept of an open society as a contrast to dogmatism and totalitarianism. His ideas about education as a key element in the formation of a free and rational society remain relevant today. In the context of modern challenges related to the information space, virtual manipulation and ideological polarization, Popper's principles can serve as important guidelines for the development of the educational system. In the context of the development of the New Uzbekistan, these ideas are especially important for building an open, modernized society based on the principles of freedom, progress and critical thinking.

References

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